

Synthesis, spectral and thermal studies of dioxouranium(VI) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-amino pyrazol-5-one

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Abstract : Some novel metal complexes of dioxouranium(VI) with Schiff bases derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde/*p*-anisaldehyde have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analyses, IR, UV, ¹H NMR spectra, thermal studies, magnetic and conductance measurements. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the complex [UO₂(ASAP)₂(Ac)₂] have been examined and was indexed. The results show that the complex belongs to the orthorhombic crystal system with unit cell dimensions : *a* = 10.48 Å, *b* = 8.03 Å and *c* = 6.03 Å. The ligands behave as neutral bidentate chelating agents in the complexes, coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The complexes are found to be monomeric and neutral with hexagonal bipyramidal geometry.

Keywords : Dioxouranium(VI), Schiff bases, thermal studies.

Dioxouranium(VI) is one of the most studied oxocations for which, a large number of complexes with varying geometries are possible¹. The Schiff base complexes of dioxouranium have aroused interest on account of their high stability, usefulness in chemical separations and their novel structural features in higher coordination numbers^{2,3}. In view of the importance of dioxouranium compounds, we have isolated and characterized some new complexes of the ligands 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzylideneamino)pyrazol-5-one (BSAP) and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)pyrazol-5-one (ASAP), derived from biologically active molecule, 4-aminoantipyrine. Both BSAP and ASAP are potential bidentate neutral ligands (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic data (Tables 1 and 2)

showed that all the complexes are mononuclear with general formula [UO₂L₂X₂], where L = BSAP or ASAP and X = Cl, Br, I, ClO₄, NCS, NO₃, Ac or SO₄/2. The molar conductance values of the complexes measured for 10⁻³ M solutions in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (Table 1) adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes⁴. The complexes are found to be diamagnetic. All the chelates are bright coloured, non-hygroscopic, stable in air and crystalline. They are soluble in methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile. Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of ligands and their metal complexes. The infrared spectrum of BSAP exhibits a broad medium intensity band ~3410 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the hydroxyl group⁵. In the spectra of all the dioxouranium complexes of BSAP, this band appears ~3425 cm⁻¹, indicating the non participation of -OH group in coordination to the metal ion. The ligand ASAP and its complexes exhibit medium intensity bands ~2830 cm⁻¹ (ν_a C-H of OCH₃) and 1425 cm⁻¹ (ν_a bending of OCH₃). The ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=N} (azomethine) observed ~1635 cm⁻¹ and ~1595 cm⁻¹ respectively in the spectra of the ligands show a downward shift to ~1600 cm⁻¹ and 1565 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes^{6,7}. These are suggestive of the participation of the pyrazol-carbonyl and azomethine groups in coordination. Thus the ligands ex-

Table I. Analytical and physical data of the complexes of BSAP and ASAP

Complex	Colour	Analytical data (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$
		Metal	C	H	N	S	
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Yellow	21.39 (21.40)	38.82 (38.80)	2.81 (2.87)	7.3 (7.5)	–	1.5
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Orange	19.79 (19.81)	35.78 (35.95)	2.52 (2.66)	6.69 (6.99)	–	3.5
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{I}_2]$	Orange	18.25 (18.37)	33.29 (33.34)	2.31 (2.47)	6.31 (6.48)	–	2.5
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Orange	20.01 (20.42)	36.91 (37.06)	2.61 (2.75)	9.31 (9.01)	–	1.7
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$	Yellow	19.98 (20.52)	40.89 (41.39)	3.21 (3.28)	7.02 (7.24)	–	10.9
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	Orange	19.12 (19.21)	34.71 (34.88)	2.17 (2.58)	5.98 (6.78)	–	7.4
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	Yellow	20.61 (20.56)	39.10 (39.39)	2.19 (2.76)	9.59 (9.67)	5.19 (5.53)	9.2
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{SO}_4]$	Orange	20.89 (20.92)	37.89 (38.00)	2.68 (2.80)	7.27 (7.38)	2.60 (2.81)	7.4
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	Yellow	24.18 (24.21)	46.10 (46.39)	3.78 (3.87)	8.41 (8.55)	–	5.7
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Orange	22.02 (22.21)	42.12 (42.55)	3.44 (3.55)	7.79 (7.84)	–	6.9
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{I}_2]$	Orange	20.15 (20.42)	41.52 (41.69)	3.17 (3.26)	7.51 (7.21)	–	7.2
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Orange	22.59 (22.97)	44.25 (44.02)	3.80 (3.67)	10.51 (10.81)	–	10.5
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$	Yellow	23.01 (23.11)	48.79 (48.93)	4.12 (4.27)	8.09 (8.16)	–	11.7
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	Orange	21.57 (21.42)	41.15 (41.08)	3.52 (3.42)	7.18 (7.56)	–	5.8
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	Yellow	23.25 (23.15)	46.51 (46.69)	3.58 (3.70)	10.05 (10.89)	6.51 (6.23)	2.5
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{SO}_4]$	Orange	23.58 (23.61)	45.71 (45.24)	3.59 (3.77)	8.25 (8.33)	3.20 (3.17)	5.4

hibit neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes coordinating through the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ groups only.

In all the complexes, a strong band characteristic of *trans* UO_2 is observed $\sim 920 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ ^{8,9}. The non-ligand bands $\sim 570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 460 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{U}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{U}-\text{O}}$ respectively¹⁰.

For the perchlorate complexes, ν_3 and ν_4 appear as strong and medium intensity bands ~ 630 and 1140 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating a monodentately coordinated perchlorate group. The medium intensity band observed $\sim 925 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) in the spectra of the perchlorate complexes fully confirms this¹¹.

The N coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group¹² is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}}$ ($\sim 2030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ ($\sim 830 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and δNCS ($\sim 470 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands. The bands $\sim 1505 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_4) and $\sim 1380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1) with a separation of about 120 cm^{-1} are suggestive of monodentately coordinated nitrate group¹³.

Acetate complexes exhibit a strong band $\sim 1584 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and medium intensity band $\sim 1370 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ respectively of acetate group. The position of these vibrations and their separation by 240 cm^{-1} are as seen for unidentate coordination of acetate group¹⁴.

Regarding sulphate complexes, the infrared spectral bands ~ 1220 , 1160 and 1075 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_3 of

chelating bidentate sulphate group¹⁵.

The electronic spectra of uranyl complexes in DMSO exhibit bands in the region $325\text{--}330 \text{ nm}$ ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$), $355\text{--}360 \text{ nm}$ ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$) and $425\text{--}430 \text{ nm}$. The band in the region $425\text{--}430 \text{ nm}$ is due to the excitation of electron from the highest filled π -molecular orbital to a non-bonding orbital on the uranium¹⁶.

In the ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands and their complexes, sharp multiple signals of the aromatic protons are noticed in the region $6.81\text{--}7.52 \text{ ppm}$. The signals due to $>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ protons and $-\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ protons are observed in the region 2.42 ppm and 3.21 ppm respectively. In the ligand BSAP and its complexes, the signal due to $-\text{OH}$ proton is present in the region 13.28 ppm ¹⁷. The presence of $-\text{OH}$ signal both in the ligand and its complexes indicate the non-involvement of $-\text{OH}$ in coordination. In the ligand ASAP and its uranyl complexes, the signal due to $-\text{OCH}_3$ is observed in the region 3.84 ppm .

The thermogravimetric curves of complexes $[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$ were recorded in the temperature range ambient to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, in an atmosphere of air (Figs. 2 and 3). The TG and DTG curves do not show the presence of water molecules, as the complexes are stable up to $254 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The decomposition of the complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ occur in three stages. The final mass loss observed agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex to its

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

oxide, U_3O_8 . The percentage of uranium found from the TG data (22.3%) is in good agreement with the experimental (20.9%) and theoretical values (20.4%). The order parameters for the first, second and third stages of decomposition are 2.5, 2 and 1 respectively. The energy

of activation for the first stage of decomposition is found to be $264.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and that for the second and third stages of decomposition are $335.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $480.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The values of ΔS for the three stages of decomposition are $204.2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $194.3 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligands (BSAP and ASAP) and their dioxouranium(VI) complexes

Ligands/Complexes	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})						
	ν_{OH}	ν_{OCH_3}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{O=U=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{U-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{U-O}}$
BSAP	3410	-	1635	1595	-	-	-
ASAP	-	2828, 1425	1638	1592	-	-	-
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	3417	-	1601	1565	920	570	460
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	3415	-	1619	1569	921	572	461
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{I}_2]$	3433	-	1609	1566	923	574	463
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	3424	-	1607	1567	925	569	459
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$	3422	-	1618	564	921	571	462
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	3431	-	1621	1567	920	573	463
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	3427	-	1617	1561	922	570	465
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{BSAP})_2\text{SO}_4]$	3422	-	1609	1563	925	573	460
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	-	2830, 1428	1619	1566	921	572	461
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	-	2831, 1426	1617	1567	922	569	463
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{I}_2]$	-	2830, 1428	1615	1559	920	571	462
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	-	2829, 1426	1609	1570	923	574	463
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$	-	2828, 1426	1615	1564	921	570	465
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	-	2830, 1425	1616	1561	919	572	460
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$	-	2835, 1426	1619	1571	921	573	461
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2\text{SO}_4]$	-	2829, 1426	1611	1568	922	572	462

Fig. 3. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$.

and $266.8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively¹⁸.

The thermogravimetric curves of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$ show a plateau up to 290°C , indicating the stability of the complex up to this temperature. The complex then decomposes in three stages with the order parameters 1, 1.5 and 1 respectively. The three stages of decomposition are denoted by DTG peaks at 299 , 402 and 528°C . The final mass loss agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex into its oxide. The percentage of uranium obtained from TG data (24.6%) is found to be in good agreement with experimental (23.9%) and theoretical values (23.1%). The ΔS values for the three stages of decomposition are 102.8 , 216.6 and $89.1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The energy of activation for the first stage of decomposition is $237.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and that for the second and third stages of decomposition are 338.4 and $284.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$ have been carried out (Fig. 4) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$. The diffraction patterns of the complex recorded 25 reflections between 2θ ranging from 10° to 50° with maxima at $2\theta = 12.6548$ which corresponds to $d = 6.0764 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed (Table 3) using Hesse and Lipson's procedure^{19,20}. The observed values fit well with orthorhombic system to give a unit cell with dimensions $a = 10.482$, $b = 8.0307$ and $c = 6.0333 \text{ \AA}$.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, a

Table 3. X-Ray diffraction data of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$

Line	<i>hkl</i>	$\sin^2 \theta$		Relative intensity (%)
		Obsd.	Calcd.	
1	010	0.0083	0.0092	36.89
2	120	0.0107	0.0098	51.11
3	001	0.0121	0.0122	100.00
4	210	0.0172	0.0175	18.70
5	111	0.0220	0.0223	36.53
6	020	0.0289	0.0289	29.03
7	120	0.0328	0.0315	4.37
8	301	0.0369	0.0355	16.97
9	121	0.0444	0.0438	28.69
10	410	0.483	0.0485	24.71
11	401	0.0551	0.0536	8.55
12	012	0.0573	0.0564	18.09
13	411	0.0622	0.0608	33.26
14	321	0.0643	0.0644	16.36
15	420	0.0710	0.0702	12.88
16	230	0.0740	0.0754	34.34
17	312	0.0796	0.0796	20.41
18	231	0.0855	0.0877	14.78
19	402	0.0907	0.0904	6.46
20	430	0.1069	0.1064	9.98
21	032	0.1142	0.1142	10.20
22	422	0.1196	0.1194	18.28
23	240	0.1253	0.1260	5.67
24	413	0.1612	0.1591	5.49
25	042	0.1746	0.1757	10.32

Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction patterns of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{ASAP})_2(\text{Ac})_2]$.

hexagonal bipyramidal structure (Fig. 5) has been tentatively proposed for all the dioxouranium(VI) complexes.

Experimental

4-Aminoantipyrine (Fluka, Switzerland), 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (Lobochemie, Mumbai, India), dioxouranium(VI) nitrate, dioxouranium(VI) acetate and dioxouranium(VI) sulphate (B.D.H., England), *p*-methoxy benzaldehyde (Lobochemie, Mumbai) were used as such. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Metal, halide and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by standard methods²¹. Perchlorate was estimated by Kurz's method²². Elemental analyses (C, H and N) of the complexes were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre (STIC), Kochi, Kerala. The IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region on a JASCO FTIR 430 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO with JASCO V550 UV-Vis spectrophotometer in the range 1000–300 nm. ^1H NMR spectrum was recorded in CDCl_3 on 300 MHz (Bruker Advance dpx-300) FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference material. The molar conductances

of the complexes in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$, CH_3OH and CH_3CN (*ca.* 10^{-3} M) were measured at 300 ± 2 K using an Elico conductivity bridge type CM 82T with a dip type cell (ec-03) fitted with platinum electrodes (cell constant is 0.94 cm^{-1}). Magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature (300 ± 2 K) were measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained on Philips X-ray diffractometer (PW 1710) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$. Thermogravimetric curves of complexes were recorded on a Mettler TG-50 thermobalance at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in air.

Synthesis of ligands :

The ligands BSAP and ASAP were synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrine and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde/4-methoxy benzaldehyde as the case may be by mixing equimolar solutions in methanol and refluxing the reaction mixture on a water bath for about 30 min. The solid product separated on cooling was suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*.

Synthesis of uranium complexes :

The complexes $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{X}_2]$ (L = BSAP/ASAP and X

Fig. 5. Proposed structures for UO_2^{VI} complexes of BSAP and ASAP.

($X = \text{Cl, Br, ClO}_4, \text{NO}_3, \text{CH}_3\text{CHOO, } \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4, \text{I, NCS}$) were prepared by the addition of methanolic solutions of the metal salt (2.5 mmol) to hot methanolic solutions of BSAP/ASAP (5 mmol) with stirring. Colour change was noticed during mixing, indicating complex formation. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 5–6 h. The solid complex separated on cooling was filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo* over P_4O_{10} .

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